

Navigating the Waste Trafficking Maze: Routes, Key Players, and Global Dynamics

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Waste trafficking poses a significant problem in today's global landscape, encompassing various environmental, social, and economic implications. Flourishing in the shadows, this clandestine industry thrives due to its profitability and the limited risk of detection in many jurisdictions. Its significance lies in the adverse impact it inflicts on local communities and the environment, whether through shipping hazardous materials disguised as non-hazardous waste, importing undeclared waste, or falsifying waste classifications to circumvent regulations. These illicit practices pose grave threats to public health, ecological balance, and sustainable development efforts.

However, despite its significance, much of waste trafficking remains shrouded in ambiguity. The clandestine nature of these activities often renders them invisible to conventional monitoring and surveillance mechanisms. Consequently, there exists a substantial gap in our understanding of the scale of this illegal trade and the networks of offenders behind it. The lack of comprehensive data and research compounds the challenge, leaving many aspects of waste trafficking obscured from scrutiny.

This veil of uncertainty significantly complicates the work of law enforcement agencies (LEAs) tasked with combating such criminal activities. The transnational dimension of waste trafficking further exacerbates

these challenges, as criminal networks exploit porous borders and regulatory disparities to evade detection and prosecution. Coordinating efforts across jurisdictions becomes increasingly arduous, as legal frameworks and enforcement capacities vary widely between countries.

Nevertheless, amidst these complexities, strides are being made towards a greater understanding of waste trafficking. Enhanced collaboration between LEAs, environmental agencies, and international organizations has led to improved intelligence sharing and operational coordination. Seizure data on illegal waste shipments or information related to police operations coming from judicial files are increasingly being used by researchers to study waste trafficking networks worldwide and draw some conclusions on the most relevant trafficking routes, actors involved and most trafficked waste types (e.g., end-of-life vehicles and e-waste).

According to one of the most recent studies that analysed all globally reported illegal shipments of end-of-life vehicles and e-waste between 2016 and 2019, Western European countries are predominantly responsible for exporting end-of-life vehicles and e-waste to countries of the Global South (Favarin et al., 2023). This dynamic showcases a troubling aspect of global waste management, where the burden of hazardous waste is shifted from richer to less equipped societies.

Illegal shipments of both end-of-life vehicles and e-waste predominantly travel from countries in the Global North to those in the Global South, with 57% of trafficking routes for both waste types following this pattern. However, 40% of the illegal flows involving end-of-life vehicles and 28% of the illegal flows of e-waste originating in the Global North are directed to other Global North countries. In a minority of cases, countries in the Global South also send their illegal waste to both Global North countries and other Global South countries (Favarin et al., 2023).

France, the UK, and Sweden are the primary exporting countries for illegal end-of-life vehicles, whereas the UK, France, Germany, and Sweden are the primary exporting countries for illegal e-waste (Figure 1). Nigeria, Poland, and Egypt serve as the main importing countries for illegal end-of-life vehicles, while China, Hong Kong, and Nigeria are the main importing countries for illegal e-waste. In general, nations shaded in dark and light blue in Figure 1 primarily act as exporters, whereas those shaded in dark and light red are identified as primary importers.

In conclusion, waste trafficking emerges as a relevant problem with far-reaching implications. While much remains unknown about this illegal trade, concerted efforts are underway to shed light on its intricacies and develop robust strategies for its prevention and enforcement. By fostering international cooperation, investing in research and innovation, and strengthening legal frameworks, the global community can strive towards mitigating the environmental and social harms wrought by waste trafficking.

TRANSCRIME BRIEF DESCRIPTION:

Transcrime (<https://www.transcrime.it/en/>) is the Joint Research Centre on Innovation and Crime at the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore of Milan. Since 1994, it has been a leading European hub for research on organized crime, economic crime, money laundering, illicit markets, and urban crime. Its spin-off, Crime&tech (<https://crimetech.it/>), translates Transcrime's research into solutions for both the public and private sectors to assess, prevent, and mitigate security and crime risks. In the field of environmental crime, Crime&tech is also a partner in the EU-funded EMERITUS project (<https://emeritusproject.eu/>), which aims to develop an investigation protocol and intelligence platform to combat waste crime. The EMERITUS project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101073874:

REFERENCES

Favarin, S., Berlusconi, G., Aziani, A., & Corradini, S. (2023). Transnational trafficking networks of end-of-life vehicles and e-waste. *Global Crime*, 24(3), 215 – 237.

Countries by their role in the trafficking network: E-Waste

Countries by their role in the trafficking network: End-of-life vehicle